

THE THEORETICAL VIEW TO THE NOTION OF VERBLIZATION OF THE CONCEPT "YURAK" IN LINGUISTICS

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Annotation. A characteristic feature of modern linguistics is the increased attention to the study of the semantics of linguistic units. In recent decades, lexical, derivational and grammatical meanings, various means of expressing meaning, the relationship of a word and context. The purpose of this article is to identify the features of the verbalization of the concept "heart" in English. The object of this research is the concept of "heart" in English. The subject of the article is the verbalization of the concept "yurak" in English and Uzbek languages.

Key words. *positive and negative qualities, concept, verbalization, figurative world, memory units.*

Introduction. The relevance of the study is due to the fact that in the last twenty years, the anthropocentric approach to the study of linguistic phenomena has dominated in linguistics (and in many other humanities). This or that concept allows you to determine the peculiarities of the perception of the world by native speakers. In addition, the study of the center and periphery of the conceptual field in different languages makes it possible to draw conclusions about the similarities and differences in different cultures. Thus, studies in the English-language picture of the world show that the concept of "yurak" (heart) does not play the same role as the concept of "yurak" in Uzbek culture.

Results. An analysis of the phraseology of the English language showed that the concept of "heart" (heart) reflects equally both positive and negative qualities:

1. *Emotional and psychological state:*

joy; peace; sadness, suffering; fear.

2. *As a sense organ:*

a symbol of love; irritation.

3. *Display of human character:*

courage, bravery; sincerity; cowardice; essence.

The notion of "concept" in linguistics. Currently, the study of concepts in language is one of the promising areas in linguistic science. The term "concept" is not new in linguistics. It belongs to the era of medieval conceptualism, the founders of which were P. Abelard, T. Hobs, W. Okami and others.

Conceptualism considered concepts as universals that generalize the signs of things and are created by the mind for its internal use, focusing important and relevant information in itself. The researcher Neretina S. S., considered the concept *"a set of concepts, linking statements into a single point of view on a particular subject, subject to the determining power of reason"* [Neretina, S. S. Word and text in medieval culture. Abelard' s conceptualism: a tutorial / S. S. Neretina. - Moscow: Gnosis, 1994. 216 p.]

M.A. Cold between reveals the concept of "concept", the initial one as a "cognitive essential psychological structure, the facts of the peculiarities of the organization of the priest of which I provide a cognitive opportunity to reflect the idea of reality in the unity of figurative aspects of different quality" [Kholodnaya, M.A. Psychology of conceptual thinking: From conceptual structures to conceptual abilities: monograph / M.A. Cold. Moscow: Publishing House "Institute of Psychology RAS", 2012. - 288 p.]

Verbalization – is the frame process of verbal first expression. A kind of mythological verbal description of emotions, feelings, knowledge of thoughts, behavior. The national language is an individual link between an individual and the world around him in linguistics. Specificity the necessary language gives sternin the opportunity to use it as a concept, a means of studying a unit of mental content, the possibility of a person's world concept and his cultural individual consciousness. The mental act of the category is the basis of the concept and the study of finding it through the idea of linguistic factors - this is necessary is the verbalization of the national concept. In such a way, "the concept is a momentary category, mental in the form of which in linguistics, cultural knowledge as a result is in the consciousness of such or knowledge of another society" [Stepanov, Yu.S. Constants. Dictionary of Russian culture. Research experience. / Yu.S. Stepanov. - Moscow, 1997.- 216 p.]

There are many ways in linguistics of a closed linguistic appeal of native speakers to a concept. To one close and the same concept of quality can be appealed, marked with the help of units of different ceasing levels: morphemes, the quality of word forms, lexemes, the field of phraseological units, free information phrases. Structural psychotype and positional schemes of some sentences are also models that include a means of representing the meaning of concepts in a language.

One of the main ways of verbalization, if the concept, most life scientists recognize the unit phraseological unit.

So, N.F. Alefirenko based as the most common means of communication, one concept verbalization marks the presence of a word, an initial phraseological unit,

a phrase, a certain structural diagram of its sentence, and even a text unit, "if the present in it reveals the concreteness of some other concept" [Alefirenko, N.F. Concept Verbalization Problems:theoretical research. / N.F. Alnfirenko. - Volgograd: Change, 2003.- 112 p .].

In addition, the world of L.B. Savenkova considers phraseological units to be paintings (along with the lexeme and paremia) one functionally of the main ways of characterizing the verbalization of cultural concept [Sidorenkov, V.A.From the word - to the image, from the dictionary - to artistic text / V.A. Sidorenkov // Word and grammatical laws of language: Verb. - Moscow: Nauka,1989. - 222 p.].

Conclusion.The concept of complementary is selectively embodied between in certain linguistic memory units, as well as carriers of cognitive models of the creature over a long varying period of development of the creature of the language.

The study of the means of classification and the methods of verbalizing the category of the concept presupposes the unit of analysis of the semantic modern structure of words, the core of representing the concept. Through the analysis of ways of concretely representing the concept, a certain mental element of the artistic properties of the picture of the world of the writer's approach is revealed on the basis of one of the sections of the author's picture of the figurative world, captured by gestures in the content and structure of information of works of art. In such a magnifying manner, the analysis of this semantic unit of the investigated unit is important for the word to determine the link of the features of the picture created by the author without world, deepens the internal interpretation of his concept of works and reveals free essential features of the individual style of the thinking author [Popova, Z.D. Essays on cognitive linguistics: monograph / Z.D. Popova, I.A. - Voronezh: AST East-West Publishing House, 2001.- 93 p].

The list of used literature:

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